

WORK LIFE BALANCE TOWARDS WORK COMMITMENT OF EMPLOYEES IN IT SECTOR INDUSTRIES (WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE CHENNAI CITY)

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Abstract

Balancing of work as well as the life is more important to the employees, no exception of IT industries. The employee one who balanced their work and life can get their job satisfaction. Satisfied employees can do better and the environment as well the work place is the part of it. Work place as well as the personal life is more responsible to give the satisfied life of an employee. Job design, autonomous in decision making, career development, job security, appreciation for their effort, flexible working time are some of the factors to bring the employees' job satisfaction. For the purpose of the study boy primary data and secondary data have been collected for the study. 250 employees have been selected from employees those who are woking in IT industries. This study concludes that the organization should help the employees to balance their work and their life to get their job satisfaction and satisfied employee contributes maximum to the organization.

Keyword: Work Life balance, IT Industries, Human resources, Development, work commitment

Introduction

In industrial world, human resource is the most significant resource as no other resource can be entirely used to generate income and wealth without the dynamic contribution of human resource. From the position of a nation, human resource can be defined as the skills, knowledge, innovative abilities, talents and aptitudes expanded in the population. From the perspectives of an individual organization, it can be defined as the sum total of important ability, skills, knowledge, attitude and behavior of a person used to raise the organizational performance. Human resource is concerned with physical, psychological, sociological, ethical and moral components of a human. At the organizational level, a human resource policy is necessary to validate the effective use of human resources to achieve organizational goals. Effective human resources management can contribute to the effectiveness of their organization. Ensuring more enthusiasm, competency, inspiration, and efficiency of the Employees in an organization can give maximum level of performance no exception to IT sector industries. Realizing the implication of human resource, many business organizations are putting their interest on improving human asset in order that the organization could reach higher level of efficiency and productivity. In this context the balancing of their work and life is more important and the industries should take care and thus brings them to achieve their

goals easily. By encouraging the employees to look after themselves and their personal commitment can gain healthy relationship and it brings the employees to work committedly. Satisfied employees can produce more for which they need satisfaction of their job. Job satisfaction depends upon their ability to manage their work and their personal life. Family as well as the work place is the responsible sources to get job satisfaction. The companies should give assurance for their peace of mind then they can do more. In this paper 250 employees have been selected from various IT Industries in Chennai. This study concludes that they are not able to cope with expectation of their employers. After the age of 45 they are interested to switch over the job and some of them started consultancies.

Significance of the Study

Work – life balance has now turned out to be a sensitive problem as it gives apparent blessings to companies and its employees. Work – life balance is a person degree can convey extra special modifications in his life and also can closely affect a society. Flexible time can provide an alternative to having to choose between work & family by allowing Employees more flexibility to balance potentially conflicting roles within them. A balanced work - life is of gain to a employees health. Individuals derive greater value from their work and from life that results in more pride and is likewise visible as a method of self- actualization. Today, a worker isn't always searching at their company only a task however they need the company to take care of their work life balance and their well-being. There is an enormous growth in work because of excessive and aggressive work environment. There's a lot of pressure on individuals, which leads to a number of problems. One should be able to create a balance between their works as well their personal life core part in achieving a work-life balance. Work-life balance has come out to be such an important area that requires a lot of research which has just begun and the findings of the research useful for individuals, for the company and for the whole society. Companies are also giving utmost importance to work-life balance to get the best out of their employees. Data have been collected from the employees those who are working in IT industry in Chennai City as a sample. The recommendations pointed in the study will provide an immense help to the IT sectors in Chennai to fruitfully design according the needs of their employees, thus improves their productivity.

Statement of the problem

Younger generation having a lot of opportunities to get employment immediate of their graduation. Managing their work and life is easier when they are young. At the same time, they are not able to cope when they turned in the middle age. Demand in life as well as their work has a new dimension. The employees those who are in IT industries work too much and there are in a position to sacrificing their life. Work and life are the important factors to get their job satisfaction. Job satisfaction gives more productivity that is the goal of the organization. Now the company concentrates on work life balance of their employees. Company is needed to construct a strategy to develop quality of work -life and work-life balance in order to satisfy the goals and needs of the company. So, the study is considered as an important one during the period.

Objectives of the Study

- To know the demographical profile of the respondents.
- To know the various programmes offered by IT companies to balance their work and their life
- To know out the factors that are all influencing the work life balance of the employees
- To know the nature of relationship between the affecting factors of work life balance with self-evaluation of performance of the employees in the IT
- To offer some suggestions made of the study.

Methodology of the study

Both primary data and secondary data have been collected for the study. Secondary data from the websites and primary data have been collected from the employees in IT industries. Data have been collected for three months from April 2022 to June 2022 using convenient random sampling technique with well-structured questionnaire through mail. Percentage analysis, rank correlation and chi square test have been used for testing the hypotheses.

Limitations of the study

1. Data have been collected from April 2022 to June 2022. The results may not be apply for other period.
2. Data have been collected only from Chennai city. The results may not be apply to other parts of the country.
3. Due to time constrain only 250 samples have been collected.

Hypotheses of the study

1. There is no association between the age, educational qualification, income, designation and experience of the respondents and their work life balance.
2. There is no significant relationship between exists in family and work related factors.
3. There is no significant relationship between work life balance and work satisfaction among the respondents.

Work Life Balance Programmes offered by IT

The benefits are divided in to three components such as general benefits, Learning objectives and Recognitions.

General Benefits:

1. Medical benefits to them and their family members.
2. Insurance
3. All applicable statutory benefits, such as retirement and pension plans.

Learning Objectives

1. Opportunities are given for further learning and improve their skills

Recognition

2. Annual incentive payouts based on performance parameters.
3. Awards for demonstrating individual abilities beyond the call of duty and participating in initiatives specific to business units.

Review of Literature:

Flora S (2022), Women employees must understand the reality and manage according to the work by scheduling all. Without this, female IT professionals would continue to be concentrated at the bottom and would not be able to climb up the work hierarchy by competing with their male counterparts. Employers are often expected to be sensitive enough to women working in IT while implementing flexible working policies, especially in a city like Chennai where there is inherent limitation. The property is the high cost of living, the distance from the workplace to the place of residence. And most are residents of the nuclear family. For spouses focused on their careers, work-life balance is an even bigger challenge. Family is the most important thing for all women, so they must take care of it by balancing work and personal life. In addition, they should take care of their own health and it is a concern for employers, employees, their partners and other family members to build a healthy society and rationally by linking work and family life.

Diane Jackson, (2020), Integrating ICT in organizations and during working from home as a way to develop theory-based recommendations for individuals for better work-life balance individual lives and let employers intentionally create a culture in what is attainable. Although today's organizational environment is marked by chaos and uncertainty, the research reviewed here supports both employees and employers prioritizing personal well-being and adopting good work habits and healthy work during integration and dependence on information and communication technology.

Madhu R Hadapad, (2020) Amid the covid-19 outbreak situation, it is very vulnerable for employees to experience stress related to working from home. Where working from home requires employees to remain productive, but on the other hand, they must gather, take care of the household and family every day during the quarantine. This will drain employees' energy, mind, and psychology where they are accustomed to working in the office every day, but now they have to work at home. Through this article, we recommend six approaches that employees can take to prevent uncontrolled stress namely communication with family, communication at work, scheduling, safety. While staying healthy, follow government regulations and limit viewing information about the covid-19 pandemic. The only flexible working arrangement in the organization is working from home. The results of these arrangements are both positive and negative. Working from home gives employees more opportunities to focus on their job duties. As the employees are experiencing new environment, and to find out the experience of the

employees on working from home when compared to work in office. The study found that willingness to work from home is entirely different and dependent on presence of their children at home, comfortable space at home, quiet environment at home and good internet connectivity.

Preeti Narendra, (2018) Practicing work-life balance is essential in an organization to retain talented employees who are productive and productive in their personal and professional goals. The policies suggested in this research paper, if made mandatory would benefit the employees at larger extent. Many IT companies have pioneered innovative policies with the recent being Infosys as coated in this paper and Accenture's leave pooling policy. The other companies should work out on the model feasible for them and drive their company towards engaging workforce, which, in turn would create a successful organization.

Ganapathi.P1, (2017) Work-life balance is still an issue that requires the attention of society. The changing nature of the global economy, where organizations often operate on a 24/7 schedule and advances in technology that allow employees to stay connected, has pushed work-to-work balance issues. Life is at the forefront of many people's concerns. In this research, I was able to understand the concept of work-life balance common in the IT industry. He also reveals different work-life balance strategies practiced by different organizations and their own employees. In the age of information technology, this research can be useful as it helps to understand the important concept that has a direct impact on employee productivity. Therefore, in order to maintain a healthy workforce, it is necessary to be able to meet and satisfy their needs. There are many areas of research in this area. This concept is a phenomenon that is being fully expanded; it opens the door to research. The area the researcher covers is limited; there are several areas that can be covered to understand the whole concept of work-life balance.

Mrs Minitha (2016) the study reveals the major factors namely working late night, sleeping patterns of the women employees; childcare issues lead to stress formation and the organizational initiatives Overcoming employee stress is a timely gift. But the work pressure is very high, so even though employees are provided, they do not enjoy the utilities. The working model of software workers prevents them from connecting with friends and family. Society is also under threat as women are seen as the link between generations passing on values, beliefs and culture.

Sakeerthi S, (2016) the study throws light into the work life balance issues of the organization and reflects the general industry scenario. The organization needs to bring in more policies to enable better work life balance and thereby facilitate better productivity. There also seems to be a lack of awareness and usage of the existing policies aimed at better work life balance. The problem of work life imbalance appears to be a matter of huge concern when looked from an outsider's point of view and so are their aftermaths. But the answers are quite simple and smooth to implement. With just a little cooperation from employers and employees, good communication and integration, the workplace will become the best place for you to relieve pressure. Apart from all the efforts of the organizations, family support is the most important issue, and this is one of the things that India lacks the most, especially for Indian working women. With the support of family and the support of the employer, the problem of work-life imbalance will no longer be an issue.

Findings of the study

1. Out of 250 respondents 56 percent of them are male and remaining 44 percent of them are female.
2. It is found that out of 250 respondents 22 percent of them are from the age group of less than 25 years, 32 percent of respondents are in the age group of 25 to 35 years, 38 percent of respondents are from age group of 35 to 45 years and remaining 8 percent of the respondents are from the age of 45 years and above. This shows that majority of the respondents are middle age group members.
3. According to their educational qualification 48 percent respondents are under graduates, 22 percent respondents are post graduates, 21 percent respondents are professionals and remaining 9 percent respondents have other qualification (Diploma and other certificate courses). It is found that the companies are interested to recruit the under graduate students for their work.
4. Out of 250 sample 67 percent of them are married.
5. It was observed that 23 percent of respondents have their monthly income of Rs.20,000 per month, 37 percent of the respondents are having monthly income lies between Rs.20,000 – Rs. 40,000, 21 percent of the respondents income lies between Rs.30,000 - 40,000 8 percent of them having Rs.40,000 – Rs.50,000 and remaining 11 percent of the respondents income lies between above Rs.50,000. Thus, it was clear from the below table that majority of the respondents income lies between Rs.20,000–Rs.30,000.
6. With regard to their designation of the respondents 37 percent of them are Process Associates, 24 percent of them are Team Leaders, 29 percent of them are Developers, 7 percent of them are Project Manager and rests of the 3 percent of the respondent are Zonal Managers. Hence it is proved that the majority of them are process associates.
7. With regard to their experience 57 percent of the respondent more than 10 years and remaining 43 of them are having experience below 10 years. Out of 57 percent of them (143 respondents) 78(112) percent of them are working in their third place (present company is their third working place. This shows that frequent switch over is happening in the IT industries.

Testing of Hypotheses

1. The calculated χ^2 value is 1.694 at 3 degrees of freedom. The probability value is 0.638 which is above 0.05, thus the null hypothesis is accepted at 5 % level of significance. So, there is no significant relationship between the age of the respondents and their Work Life Balance
2. The calculated χ^2 value is 5.724 at 3 degrees of freedom and the probability value is 0.126 which is above 0.05, thus the null hypothesis is accepted at 5 % level of significance. So, it is concluded that there is no significant relationship between the educational qualification of the respondents and their work life balance

3. The calculated χ^2 value is 8.095 at 4 degrees of freedom and the probability value is 0.044 which is less than 0.05. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected at 5 % level of significance. So, it is concluded that there is significant relationship between the monthly income of the respondents and their work life balance
4. The calculated χ^2 value is 10.335 at 3 degrees of freedom whereas the probability value is 0.016 which is less than 0.05. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected at 5 % level of significance. So, it is found that there is significant relationship between the designation of the respondents and their work life balance
5. The calculated χ^2 value is 4.139 at 3 degrees of freedom and the probability value is 0.126 which is above 0.05. Thus the null hypothesis is accepted at 5 % level of significance. So, it is concluded that there is no significant relationship between the total years and experience of the respondents and their of work life balance
6. There is significant association exist in family and work related factors

Chi- Square Test Statistics		
	Total work	Total family
Chi-Square	82.680 ^a	54.961 ^b
Df	16	9
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000
Decision	Significant	Significant
	H0 Rejected	H0 rejected

P values are **.000 which is less than .05**. So the researcher decided to reject H0 and Accept H1, so there is association between family and work, it means various family circumstances will affect the total work of an Employees.

7. There is no significant relationship between work life balance and work satisfaction among the respondents.

ANOVA						
	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	19.402	2	9.701	.983	.378	Not significant H0 Accepted
Within Groups	986.987	100	9.870			
Total	1006.388	102				

It is clear that the P value of **.378 which is greater than .05**. So null hypothesis is accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected. The level of work life balance and work satisfaction among IT Employees are not associated with each other, they are varied to each other in accordance with various perspectives of Employees.

- IT sector should provide greater resource accessibility to perform work as per pre-determined schedule; it will help them to balance their work and life.
- The IT sector employees need good support from their superiors regarding the

management of stress such as deadlines and work schedule.

- IT companies have to implement proper employees management techniques, such as optimum workload, flexible working time, and compressed work week and so on to establish balance between work and life.
- Conflict and dispute among employees should be monitored in order to enhance greater work-life balance and work satisfaction.
- The study suggested that IT companies want to frame suitable work-life balance policies to get stress-free work atmosphere, flexible work hours, leave arrangements and work sharing and so on.

Conclusion

The present study integrates the outcomes of empirical analysis of the work - life balance towards work commitments of IT employees with special reference to selected IT sectors in Chennai city. Work-life balance is an emerging phenomenon in the context of modern-day organizations. Organizations need to pay more attention to strengthening HR policies to increase their number of employees. IT sector Employee's workforce is emergent and their involvement in the organization is valuable to its expansion. It is considered crucial for the companies to recognize Employees by offering more suitable work-life balance measures to them. Providing better and healthier work-life balance is significant for Employees working in the IT sector. This study identified that demographic profile of Employees working in the IT industries were found consistently. IT sectors Employees have enough awareness on work culture, and their expectation to increase work-life balance was also high in the IT Company. This study concludes with the result indicates that the work - life balance has no significant influence on work satisfaction; there is no positive relation to exist. But Employees' have high level of agreement between the significant influences of family in total work of Employees.

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